

Review on Techniques of intrusion detection and snort performance Bottlenecks, Solution and Packet Inspection

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Abstract

The paper present review different types of Intrusion detection techniques, historical Foundation of snort intrusion detection System, snort IDs components, review on Snort

performance bottleneck under higher Traffic networks, proposed solution, snort Packet inspection and snort pattern matching Algorithms.

Introduction

As a result of vast increase in technology and lack of integrating good security practices in software and hardware design which has leads to backdoors, bugs and e.t.c. A number of network

attacks are increasing dramatically, ranging from denial of services, IP spoofing eavesdropping, mitnick,(MITM) man in the middle attack masquerading and malware attacks (Snehal and Jadhav,2010).These attacks have made

traditional network security mechanism . In effective, which requires additional defense mechanism which can analyze, detect and mitigate these types of attacks ,such as intrusion detection system, Honey pot and firewall, usually these devices are used as parameter security measures. Despite application of these devices in a network, some network requires more security measures to prevent its transmitted information from being attack. Some of these measures includes encryption, Digital signature and secure socket layer and Transport layer security (TLS, SSL) to secure transmitted data. In case of network infrastructures protection a tamper resistance nodes are develop to safe guard some attacks (Yong ,Wang et. al, 2006).Beside the describes security measures, many organization bring in to implementation of assets or IT equipment protection mechanisms (Technical) and procedures in terms of policies ,education and awareness program.

Knowledge of the intruder

With the rapid growing number of automated tools, discussion group, forums and skill intruders, has lead to the increase in attack

sophistication. The knowledge gathered by intruder by taken part in online hackers forums has resulted in a raise of knowledge needed to exploit computing resources. Furthermore, increasing number of open source or free automated tools used to determine and launch attack in the computing are taken as one among factors that increases the knowledge of attackers, nowadays, intruder has not required any much experience and skills in carrying their activities as a number of system vulnerabilities can be found for free in the internet.

Intrusion

The term intrusion can be described as a violation of security policy of systems with the aims of destroying or de-stabilizing its activities. In other word Intrusion is an unauthorized access to the network computing devices by the legitimate or un-legitimate user. Many techniques are used by the intruders to get access to the network computing device illegally. Some of the popular known network intrusions include IP spoofing, denial of services; port Scanning, WEP cracking, Masquerading and Malware attack. Basically,

based on the architectural view of any network system, vulnerabilities can be seen or explore in the three levels of a system which constitutes the system levels, also network levels and system level which constitutes the operating system level and the application level, therefore most intrusions to company assets IT equipment were categorized as either intrusion at a network level, operating system level and the user application level.

Intrusion Detection System

Nowadays, intrusion detection system is the most widely used and top growing network security technology used by many industries. These systems unlike firewall and other security related systems or mechanism configure as network parameter security such as Honey pot which is mainly designed to detect any intrusion into a network. According (Rani, 2009) many different forms of open source and commercial intrusion detection are obtainable to the best of user requirement e.g snort, NitroGuard and Niksu net detector. However, according to (Geddes Linda, 2009) says it has been estimated that the open source intrusion detection system have higher popularity in middle size industries than the commercial

systems. These was as a result of high cost, real time support and ability to be configured to suite the user needs and platform implementations. The attractiveness of the open source software in most of our research institution and academic environment resulted from many qualities which open source software has, such as detailed documentation, online forum support and ability to be customized to meet user requirements.

In addition, many objectives are assigned to be achieved while deploying Intrusion detection system, one among is to design the network behavior based on system events that can detect network intruders. The design system operation is basically set to be based on difference phases each of which there is a specific task set to be accomplished. In the data collection phase, all information about system behavior is gathered, and in a pre-processing phase the input data to be used in the IDS system is generated, this is achieve by pre-processing the network traffic data, also in the straining phase, the pre- processed data served as the bases through which network user normal behavior is known by the system. Therefore,in

the detection phase, is a phase from which attacks were detected by comparing the gathered behavior of a system and that of the present pattern. In addition, The detected intrusion in the network alert were generated and send to the log files and these alert are usually used by the system administrators(Gascon Hugo, *et. al*, 2011). Generally, the network user behavior is classified using difference techniques, such artificial intelligent and rule induction or neural network. Indeed, through these classifications many network intruders or intrusions are discovered. Network throughput is the main factor to be considered when designing IDS with anomaly detection techniques, as and as well primary factors that may ensure efficient performance of the IDs is to fit with network speed for effective detection of intruded packets in the network effectively without packet dropping, and higher false alarm under rigorous condition, also efficiency of the pattern matching algorithm to inspect the packet payload, the designed system should have the ability to monitor and analyze both inbound and outbound network traffic. In a higher network architectures, distributed intrusion detection

system with sensors are used in conjunctions with load balancing traffic splitter to provide load balancing between different sensors . These will ensure minimum used of resource and ease cost of deployment. Similarly, two (2) distinct responses are adopted by intrusion detection systems if an attack is detected in the network, namely passive response and active response (Bahram and Bahrami, 2011). However, in response to attack using passive mode, the traffic is not denying access to the network rather, the incident is recorded in the log file and an alert is generated and send to notify the administrator, while in active response a reset connection packet is send to allow the packet to be ignored entry in to the network. Designed of these intrusion detection systems is hardware or software based, to achieve good performance gain over its Internal pattern matching algorithm a software based implementation is chosen(**white paper intelcore,2010**). There are many functions perform by both network and host based intrusion detection system such as the ability to monitor configurations and vulnerabilities, and the system security policy violation as well as

how outside users have access to the system and file integrity (Ashoor and Gore, 2011). In network environment any violations of security policies such as illegal connection to network port or hidden malicious scripts are detected and the events are recorded in the logs file or alarm is generate to alert the system administrator. According to (Gascon Hugo, *et. al*, 2011) point out that the logged events are used for further pre-question about the policy violation like fire rules re-configurations and other security device configuration.

Network Intrusion detection system

Network intrusion detection system is deployed in the network segment to observe and analyzes incoming network packets. The captured and analyzed data is used to detect known attacks using the stored patterns or signatures of the database. And also all of illegal activities are detected by scanning traffic for example illegal connection to the network services such as HTTP SPOP and SMTP. In addition, network intrusion detection systems are also referred as packet-sniffers . Because it has the ability to captures and compare the packets passing through the communication medium(Ashoor

and Gore, 2011). Some network intrusion detection system are anomaly based, as such the observed normal system behavior pattern were against incoming network packets. Basically, the general network architecture of network intrusion detection is based on the four different models namely, event modules, data- module, analyzes modules and response module, these modules collectively performed the intrusion detection function based on the information gathered.

Host-Based Intrusion detection

A host in a network or attached stand alone system configured to monitor traffics that will cause harm to system resources, files and data, process and threads or cause malefactions to the system resources such as memory or drive i.e. virus, Trojan worms, worm and spywares can be detected or prevented entry in to the system and log the attack details in the log files for a system administrators. According to Suman (2010) defined host-based intrusion detection as software based intrusion detection system usually installed in the host computer that requires specific configuration. Based on the

operating system, the host intrusion detection system is configured to deal with detection of security policy violations by analyzing the host local logs audit files, software calls and others. Basically, many types of host-based intrusion detection system combined both intrusion detection and prevention functions like network intrusion detection systems. HIDS analyzes data originated from local host to find malicious traffic. Many host information are analyzed by HIDS that includes event and kernel logs. Also it tracks program access to system resource and maintained a match between program abnormal behavior and system normal behavior. McAfee intrusion detection and prevention system is one example of HIDPS used to interrupt system call and network traffic before being executed in the host systems. These are in order to ensure full protection of the system resource and applications.

Signature based detection techniques

Signature detection techniques is an intrusion detection techniques from which a record of known attack signature is kept in the database and intrusion is detected by comparing signature pattern and the pattern that exist in the packet payload (abnormal user activities that violate the well being of the system). In addition, network packet is search to indentify malicious byte by an inner pattern matching algorithm. In this technique the signatures is **very easy to form**, for efficient pattern matching to be done in a reasonable amount of power is needed in respect to a specific number of rules. In addition, signatures of exploit are easily generated based on the specific service port it communicated with, for examples, system that communicate through the following services Domain name server (DNS), internet control message protocol (ICMP) and SMTP. But fixed behavioral pattern detections, increasing number of novel attack and inability to detect self modifying worm and virus had become catastrophic to this techniques (*Jyothsna et. all, 2011*). Similarly, advanced technologies are used to avoid these techniques also increasing in number of attack signatures contributed to the performance

degradation(Gascon Hugo *et.al*,2011).In addition, the performance degradation of the IDS during pattern matching is over come by deploying the system in multi processors and multi Gigabit network card a proposed system based on hardware such as Application specific integrated circuit (ASIC), Field programmable Gate array (FPGA) and ternary Addressable memory (TC(Gao, 2006) to enhance the performance of signature pattern matching of the system engine.

inform of alert or logging the incident. The above model addressed the problems of false negative by updating the model profile(Patel, 2008).

Anomaly based detection techniques

Basically, in anomaly based detection network behavior is learned and the learned network behavior is compared with the incoming network traffic to detect an intrusion. (Sandhu *et.al* 2011). In this technique many possibilities are used to detect anomalous behaviors. Data such as Kernel information, system log records information software running information and normal packet characteristic is collected and stored. Therefore, any deviation to this gathered information is recorded as anomalous metric used to measure and detect the deviation of the system behavior and Alarm is usually generated if deviation is found. The model development comprises of three different stages namely parameterization, training and detection stage(Ning and Jajodia, 2001).However, as the working stile of this technique defines on some protocols as such it s problem in rule setting and produce higher rate of false alarm the

In the figure 2.1 given above illustrate the misuse detection model.

The model use pre-defined signature pattern defined in its database to detect anomalous packet using pattern matching algorithm if the match is found then a response is generated

strength of this techniques over signature based engines is its ability to be able to deter any novel attack whose pattern has deviated normal traffic pattern (Ning, and Jajodia, 2001).

Figure 2.1 Anomalous Detection Techniques Model (Patel, 2008)

In the Figure 2.2 given above illustrate the anomalous detection model. The detection is based on the deviation of the model system behavior as described in the section 2.3.5 the incoming data packet is analyzed and a significant changes is observed and then response is generated based on either logging or alerting the system administrator. In addition for the false alarm generated mostly by this model is addressed through profile upgraded and changes

made within the system or network traffic behavior is observed (Patel, 2008).

Historical background of SNORT

Snort intrusion detection is an open source intrusion detection which use a signature based detection techniques. Snort tool was originally design as a packet sniffer in 1998 by Marty Roesch which was named APE (Linda Geddes, 2009). Despite the function perform by the APE, Marty Roesch wanted to have a sniffer that can have additional feature or that can perform many functions such as ability to function in many different Operating systems platforms. Windows Linux and UNIX are few among the interested operating system platform Marty Roesch wanted to have snort tool working on. Another desire by the Marty Roesch is the ability for the sniffer (APE) to display multiple difference network packets in the unique form. Much advancement on sniffer features come to being including the sniffer ability to not only capture packet but it can also filter it. This application is named libpcap. However, In December, 1998,snort become packet storm which has only one thousands and six hundred (1600) lines of codes that are compiled in only

two files. Marty s uses snort to perform many work such as monitoring his cable modern and debugging his network applications at around January 1999 snort become a fully features signature based detection system. In addition on December 1999 a new version of snort 1.5 was released, which was used as a light weight intrusion detection system at that time snort used many different plug-in that are being used now. The latest version of snort tool came to being in 2003 snort 2.x.x.x has 75,000 line of code.

Snort Intrusion Detection System

In most industries snort had become widely adopted as network perimeter security mechanism, snort provide According to Rani and Singh (2010) defined snort as a single threaded network security mechanism that can work based on four difference configuration mode, Packet sniffer mode, packet logger mode, detection mode and prevention mode or inline mode. Snort is an open source network intrusion detection system which is configured in a network PC as a network IDS. However, snort is incorporated in third party solutions, snort tool get wide acceptance by many

industries all over the world with millions of a download. The detection of malicious traffic by snort is done by using transmission control protocol stack. A deep packetpayload inspection is done by matching the observed packets and pre-defined snort signature. In a network, snort can be implemented in many different platforms such as Linux, FreeBSD, windows but snort has higher performance when deployed in a Linux platform because of its higher supportability, stability, security and reconfigurable network subsystem. Also snort performance is optimized by using Berkeley filter (BPF) using BPF only interested network packet are allowed to pass for analyzes by the snort components (Terrence *et. al*, 2010). However, Snort packet logging performance and its fault alarm produces during packet inspections depends on the accuracy of its configurable components. i.e snort packet grabbing mechanism (lipcap library). In addition the accuracy of how detection can inspect the packet for malicious give rises to the snort better performance. Similarly, these components are separated into different dependent components; however, the first component is the packet capturing through which the transmitted network

is tossed in the snort. After the libcap accomplished its functions the captured packet in raw form is passed to the decoder components after the raw packet is being decoded or prepared for pre-processing its send in to the snort next components for pre-processing which is the pre-processor component. The pre-processor perform many task on the received packets before sending it to the detection engine, among the functions are packet examinations, manipulations, and defragmentation and packet classifications. However, the detection engine which is the main snort components perform a test to check whether the packet is malicious to detect intrusion and the result obtained is send to the final plug-in which is the snort output. The figure 2.1 shows the different snort components

Snort Decoder

The packet received by the snort tools needs to be further prepared for further processing by the snort components, at this phase the protocol elements is decoded by the specific decoder e.g. IP protocol, this make up series of packet decoders whose functions is to work up the network stack, decoding down from the first OSI model layer (data link frame) up to last layer services such as SMTP. The decoded packets are kept in the data structure ready to serve as an input to the remaining components (snort document, 2010). firstly, the decoder start with data link frame Ethernets, token ring and then proceed to decodes the Internet protocol and followed by the transmission transfer protocols and universal data protocol (Andrew,2004). In accordance to (Sallah *et.al*, 2011) The information generated by the snort decoder is used for further processing by snort detection engine and pre-

processor (snort article 2009).The libpcap used in Linux and Unix operating system and the winpcap used by most of windows operating system serve as an interfaces use to tossed unprocessed network packet from the network interface (NIC) to the snort tool decoding engine. This type of network interface includes Ethernet interface, SLIP, PPP, and e.t.c.

Snort pre-processor

Pre-processor is the next to the packet decoder components in the snort tools which perform numerous operations on the decoded network packets also enabled plug-in e.g. remote procedure call (RPC) is use in analyzing packet for a distinct malicious behavior some of the packet analyzes by the pre-processor includes hypertext transfer protocol (HTTP) and port scanning. In addition many pre- processors plug-in are utilized to extend the functionality of the snort tool. The decoded packet from the decoding component of snort is passed to specific pre-processor in case of many preprocessors module for analyzes against a pre-defined attack pattern examples RPC, Port scanning Http and the encryption verifier plug-in. Indeed, preprocessor plug-in has a general

syntax of
“*preprocessor<name_of_preprocessor>:<configuration_option* (www.syngress.com) . In addition, to protocol analyzes by the pre-processor another function was highlighted by (muthurengunathan *et. al*,2009) that express the capability of pre-processor to defragment the fragmented packet before forwarding it to the detection engine, this has advantages, because attackers used fragmented packet format to thwart the IDS detection capability. In addition to these functions pre-processor perform packet classification and packet dropping.

Snort Detection Engine

Snort detection Engine is most important segment of the snort IDS. The detection engine act almost like a processor in a computer, indeed, the detection engine detects any intrusion which is associated with the packet data by matching it with the set of rules in the signature database. If a match is found, an appropriate action is taken against the detected intrusion such as alert , send to the output plug-in or logged, otherwise the packet is dropped (Intrusion not detected) (Geddes and Linda

2009). In addition, work by (Terrence *et al.*, 2010) snort detection engine is a customizable components that allow many different pattern matching algorithm to be configured i.e. Aho-corasick, Boyer Moore and many more pattern matching algorithm. The performance of these components depends on its inner core pattern matching algorithm and efficiency to match the pre-defined signature pattern with the incoming packet pattern. Therefore, this makes snort detection engine to be the most computationally intensive because more CPU time is required to perform pattern matching against all the pre-defined thousands of rules.

Snort Alerting

The term plug-in is a source program code designed independently of any application used to extend the overall large application functionality. Plug-in programs allow user to customize large application to suite his requirement. According to Shangjie, (2011) snort support many different plug-in that adds more capability to it which include pre-processor, detection engine, plug-in and output plug-in. The output snort plug-in displays many different forms of input including my SQL

Server. Alerting and logging component are components which generate result from the output of snort detection engine, when a match is found with a pre-defined signature snort send alert to the log in files in a real time. The alert generated by snort can be stored in a databases, log files, Syslog servers, SNMP traps, and WinPopup Messages. For examples MySQL. However, at this component many different tools can be used by snort which includes different number of plug-ins for various programs such as Perl, PHP and provision of logs via a web interface. Similarly, logs can be stored in a different formats such as text files:var/log/snort or in other applications examples mysql. Many protocols are used such as SNMP traps and another one popularly known as win popup messages (Geddes and Linda, 2009).

Performance of snort under high traffic network

Snort performance limitation can be counter measured by using difference techniques, one among is by removing the traditional network stack and socket interface mechanism. Despite, contributions made to enhance snort performance none of these solutions are adopted

by the snort manufacturer due to the un-changed snort deployment settings. Snort experience performance degradation when it is subjected to the high traffic network, these problems facing snort had attracted attentions of many researchers toward analyzing snort performance under different platforms and reviewing the general architecture of snort to meet the modern day to day network traffic requirements. However, as described, according to w snort article (2009) , snort packet execution is done sequentially, packet moves from one component to another, and only one packet is processed by these components at a time. Therefore, the incoming packets are firstly buffered in either network interface kernel or libpcard. This can result to the packet dropping when the buffer is full when snort is configured under higher traffic network. In addition, Sallah, (2008) point out that snort is installed in different platforms either in Linux, windows or FreeBSD and its performance is highly consumed malicious packet detection and rule matching by the detection engine. The increasing network traffic rate to almost more than of Gbs has made it necessary to increase the snort detection

efficiency to avoid packet dropping by the snort s detection engine. However, in accordance to Sallah,(2008) refusing to efficiently and quickly address the performance increasing in today s higher rate network technology will result to a higher lost of organization network resources .Indeed, Under snort performance in packet inspection will guarantees the network to be attacked by intruders. The overall snort performance problem, is as a result of inefficient malicious packet processing and signature matching by the detection engine under high traffic network (Kahtani, 2009). The (Joshi,2011) the snort performance limitation has gone beyond in ability to perform well in a higher traffic network, the inability for snort tools to detect the unknown malicious code too, as a result of this (Joshi,2011) had proposed systems that used entropy based anomaly detection and integrates it with real-time snort. The proposed system takes advantages of both anomaly and signature based detections. But the main drawbacks of this propose system is, it produce higher no of false alarm because it uses the current data to detect anomalies.

Moreover, ability to identify and ignores processing of identical malicious packets will limit the processing overhead and increased the performance of snort tool. A proposed approach by (Roozbahani *et. al.*,2010) re-structures snort architecture to be able to detect the identical attacks and discard it before sending it to the detection engine(reducing work load of the snort processing components).

The design system consists of pre-processor put at the network entrance whose task is to convert the capture packet in to standard form. Secured mobile agent and few snort tools are configured in some selected network host.Also, no doubt implementing this had reduced the processing overhead and increase the system performance of the network. Moreover, study conducted by (Kahtani,2009) evaluate the performance of snort throughput based on the benign and normal traffic and proposes a snort configuration that will ensure good performance of snort tool. The study is conducted under budget values different from the current default value (300) of Linux configuration networking subsystem, this demonstrated that the performance of snort can

be increased in both malicious and normal packet processing by choosing the NAPI budget values smaller than the default value of 300.However, the changing of NAPI default parameter was because the snort s detection engine requires more CPU power to perform rule and string matching.

Network packet inspection

Packet inspection or content matching is the major task done in intrusion detection system carried out by the detection engine (Hassan and AbdulRashid, 2012). To ensure the effectiveness of the snort intrusion detection any incoming packets must be checked against pre-defined signature in the system database by the pattern matching algorithm, which will match the packets strings against the signature (Chamley,2011). However, because of more technological way of attacking computing devices and using network as medium more sophisticated and efficient way of inspecting packets is needed (Abhishek *et. al.*,2012).Snort intrusion detection system interact with internet protocols such as transmission control protocols stacks in order to capture and examine the overall network packet or payload in order to

identify those packet that will present harm to the computing resource or attacks such as denial of service attack which is the most common type of network attack and buffer overflow attack and man in the middle attack. The network packet strings of these attacks are compared against pre-defined signature to find the anomalous.

Snort Packet Inspection

Packet inspections are considered compulsory for any incoming packet in the network in order to ensure secure and congestion free network. This is carried out to identify whether the packets has matches with any signature defined in the system signature database. The signatures are represented based on attack type e.g. Vulnerability, virus, worm and denial of service attacks. However, there are many types of packet inspection carried out by network security system such as firewall and intrusion detection systems. In a state full packet inspection only three layers of protocol are examine source transport layer address which includes transmission control protocol and user datagram protocol (TCP or UDP), destination transport IP address also network layer protocol

that includes internet protocol of the source system and the IP address of the destination system(Chaudary and Sardana,2011). However, the service used to connect from the destination system is inspected, like File transfer protocol and hypertext transfer protocol e.tc.In medium packet inspection ,the communication between internal system and outside network is carried out via a proxy server application which provides packet filtering capabilities. But in deep packet inspection which is considered the best according to Hassan,(2012) the whole packet payload is inspected by the security appliances. Indeed, more efficient techniques are needed in these types of deep packet inspection while using pattern matching algorithms for finding malicious packets. However, according to (Zhang, 2010) these presents a lot of challenges because it requires time for the snort pattern matching algorithms e.i. boyer moore, Ac corasicks and wu- moore and their modified families to thoroughly inspect a network incoming packets, also it faces a lot of challenges which includes consumption of almost half of snort processing time as rated according to (Hassan and Abdulrashid,2012).

More challenges are faced by the pattern matching algorithms as described by (Chaudhary and Sardan,2011).Similarly, according to the (Charras and Iecroq, 2005) in a packet inspection ,text are scan using a window which has a fixed size, usually donated by a letter.The end of the window and the text are arranged at the begging of the text. Indeed, at this point an attempt is made by comparing the window characters with that of the text and in which a match is observed or mismatched and this leads to the shift of the window to the subsequent pattern until when the ends of the text is reached. This technique is known as a sliding window mechanism. The snort intrusion detection system used pattern group sizes of up to a thousand or greater than, therefore, the byte size of packet that snort can search at once is averagely 600 to 800 byte and this can be done almost 200,000 times per second (Norton,2004)

Performance of snort in Packet Inspection

Pattern matching algorithm is considered as the core component of snort signature based intrusion detection system. Pattern matching algorithm matches the captured packet with the signature database to check whether any

malicious intent exists. According to Sallah (2009) approximately 30%-60% of the total snort detection time is spent in signature matching which contribute to the slowdown of the snort performance. In addition, more number of attacks is seen now which raise the number of signature generated daily as well this will leads to the increase of the searching time. Basically, the number of snort tool rules increased from 1,542 at 2003 to almost nine thousands, nine hundred and forty five rules in 2011 and couples with increase in network traffic every eight months. Therefore, these increase in rules generated and the network traffics, slowdown the performance of snort IDS, to countermeasure these problems an efficient signature or pattern matching algorithm which will efficiently compare the capture packets with the signature database should be proposed. Similarly, this efficiency of most snort detection algorithm had became a catastrophic to most snort intrusion detection system; accordance (Afshin *et. al*,2009) propose a collaborative environment of mobile agent to uptimizes the performance of snort for detecting malicious traffic in a network where snort is deployed as network detection

system. The proposed approach used any pattern matching algorithms in an integrated framework, to address the problem of traditional intrusion detection approach which limits the power of snort detection to only local network where its algorithm is restricted. Indeed, the proposed approach was designed based on the Microsoft future generation approach in which users will receive or subscribed required services from the web with the need of installing the packets in their system. In this approach the powerful algorithm that snort depends on for detecting malicious traffic is going to be received as a service from various trusted servers world-wide after being verified. Based on the traditional approach adopted by the snort detection system ,the detection rate is 60% while with adoption of this new system, the anomalies detection rate is increased to almost 98%.The major advantage of this approach is the increase in detection rate by introducing more powerful distributed detection or pattern matching algorithm provided as a service to the snort worldwide and ability for the network snort to detect the previously detected malicious traffic without requiring any services from the trusted servers as

any record of newly detected malicious traffic is added in the snort local signature database. In addition, based on system performance evaluation, in any 1000 different connections to the network almost 321 are attacks and out of these number only 51 are non repetitive attacks and the remaining 270 are repetitive attacks which limit the number of connections to the server. The major drawbacks to this approach is the number of traffics in the network is increase and resulted in the network performance decrease or even result to packet dropping experienced by other snorts that utilized the old traditional pattern matching algorithms.

Snort Detection engine and pattern matching algorithm

Detection engine is the heart of snort detection system which performed the task of comparing the capture packet with the pre-defined signature in its database. However, according to (Hasan and AbdulRashid, 2012) the performance of snort detection engine depends on the efficiency of its matching algorithms, similarly, improvement of the algorithm s performance will ensure the accurate and efficient malicious packet detection at the snort

detection engine. Many works were carried out toward modifying the existing snort pattern matching algorithms.

Conclusion

The paper presents challenges of snort tools in packet inspection and proposed work to bring end to the snort tool performance bottleneck, also in the paper snort packet inspections and how other work had contributed to its performance bottlenecks.

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